

Efficient Class C prediction of PVD-improved soft clay settlements

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ABSTRACT

Soft clays exhibit significant challenges in geotechnical engineering due to their low permeability, high compressibility, and susceptibility to settlement under applied loads. These geological factors pose unique difficulties in predicting long-term settlement accurately and efficiently, particularly through Class C prediction methods that involve iterative processes with complex numerical models. To address these challenges, this study presents an efficient approach for Class C prediction of long-term settlement in soft clays. This approach integrates Bayesian updating with structural reliability methods (BUS) and the general simplified Hypothesis B method which is a semi-analytical method based on one-dimensional elastic visco-plastic (1D EVP) model. Unlike previous research that used Response Surface Model (RSM) with polynomial function for consolidation evaluation, the proposed approach enhances both accuracy and performance consistency under varying conditions. Additionally, by leveraging analytical solutions instead of iterative small-time steps required by Finite Element Method (FEM) or Finite Difference Method (FDM), the computational efficiency is also enhanced. The effectiveness of the proposed approach is demonstrated through its application to an embankment improved with prefabricated vertical drain (PVD) in Ballina, New South Wales, Australia. Comparative analyses demonstrate that the predicted settlements from this study, using only the monitoring settlement data collected prior to the 76th day of the project, align closely with the results from established RSM and FEM-based Bayesian back analysis approaches. The obtained results also indicate that the predicted settlements, based on 76 days of monitoring data, closely match field measurements at various depths, whether relying solely on settlement data or integrating additional pore water pressure data. For the Ballina embankment, over 40,000 consolidation analyses required for a single BUS simulation can be completed within 10 h using the general simplified Hypothesis B method, compared to months it might take with FEM or FDM approaches. This makes the proposed approach a practical tool for geotechnical engineers, enabling reliable settlement predictions early in the project timeline while maintaining low computational costs.

1. Introduction

Class C prediction, introduced by Lambe (1973), incorporates field monitoring data into back analysis to achieve an optimum fit between predictions and measurements. This approach leverages real-time data to enhance the accuracy of settlement predictions. However, achieving reliable Class C prediction with reasonable computational costs remains challenging due to the inherent complexities of soft clay behaviour, the

sophisticated modelling required, and the computational demands of both consolidation and back analysis.

Soft clays exhibit complex behaviour over time, experiencing significant deformation and settling under applied loads. To model these behaviours, rigorous constitutive models incorporating highly nonlinear partial differential equations have been proposed. Notable examples include 1D EVP model proposed by Yin and Graham (1996) and soft soil creep model introduced by Vermeer and Neher (1999). These models are

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Fig. 1. Two cases for obtaining settlement at any locations

typically solved using numerical methods such as FDM (Yin and Graham, 1996; Huang et al., 2023) and FEM (Zhu and Yin, 1999; Vermeer and Neher, 1999; Huang and Griffiths, 2010; Chen et al., 2023). However, achieving reliable predictions with these methods requires iterative simulations with small time steps, which are computationally demanding and require a solid understanding of nonlinear constitutive models. This complexity poses challenges for practical applications by non-specialists. To improve computational efficiency, researchers, such as Mollon et al. (2009), Li et al. (2015), Hamrouni et al. (2021) and Tian et al. (2022) have explored surrogate models such as RSM to approximate computationally demanding models such as Finite Difference or Finite Element models with polynomial functions. While RSMs offer efficiency gains, their accuracy can vary depending on the choice of polynomials and the quality of training data, potentially leading to biased long-term settlement predictions (Zhang et al., 2010; Tian et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2021; Tian et al., 2023). In contrast, the general simplified Hypothesis B method, initially proposed by Yin and Feng, 2017) and further extended by Yin et al. (2022), builds upon 1D EVP constitutive relationship and the concept of equivalent time (Bjerrum, 1967; Yin and Graham, 1989; Yin and Graham, 1994). This method is a semi-analytical method which avoids the iterative small-time steps in numerical approaches, significantly improving computational efficiency of consolidation analysis. The simplified method has proven effective as a reliable approximation for consolidation modelling in multi-layer soft soils subjected to both instantaneous and complex loading conditions (Feng et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2021; Yin et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2023).

Additionally, the back analysis required to interpret and adjust predictions based on observed data introduces further complexity, necessitating effective solutions to efficiently handle highly nonlinear problems (Jiang et al., 2020). Probabilistic Bayesian back analysis has emerged as an effective tool for understanding uncertain soil behaviours. It enables the incorporation of various information sources, including engineering judgment, field measurements, and observation errors, in a consistent manner (Zhang et al., 2010; Hsein Juang et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2016; Zheng et al., 2018; Jiang et al., 2018b). However, the numerical and analytical methods for solving the highly nonlinear Bayesian back analysis problem are computationally intensive and not straightforward to implement. The challenge arises from the mathematical intractability of inferring the posterior distribution, which involves solving a high-dimensional integrals (Hsein Juang et al., 2013; Jiang et al., 2018a; Zheng et al., 2018). Sampling methods such as Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) have gained popularity for directly sampling from the posterior distribution, avoiding the need to evaluate high-dimensional integrals in Bayesian back analysis problems (Gilks et al., 1995; Gelman et al., 2004). However, MCMC simulations face challenges in high-dimensional problems due to slow convergence and

difficulties in determining burn-in periods (Ching and Wang, 2016; Straub and Papaioannou, 2015). To address these challenges, Straub and Papaioannou (2015) proposed the BUS approach, which transforms the Bayesian back analysis problem into an equivalent structural reliability problem that can be efficiently solved using Subset Simulation (SuS). Compared to MCMC, BUS requires fewer simulations to achieve convergence, especially for high-dimensional problems involving numerous uncertain parameters (Straub and Papaioannou, 2015; Jiang and Huang, 2016; Jiang et al., 2018a; Betz et al., 2018; Jiang et al., 2020; Tian et al., 2022). BUS has been previously demonstrated as successful in Class C prediction of Ballina embankment by Tian et al. (2022) and Tian et al. (2023) integrating with RSM and FEM models respectively.

This study aims to develop an efficient approach that can be used by practitioners to reliably predict the long-term settlement of soft clays during the early stages of construction. For this purpose, we utilized the general simplified Hypothesis B method to improve the efficiency of consolidation analysis and the BUS method to improve sampling efficiency. This study is the first to demonstrate the successful substitution of RSM, FEM or FDM models with the general simplified Hypothesis B method within a Bayesian updating framework. This efficient framework enables engineers to make timely decisions in soft soil engineering, leading to cost-effective outcomes. To evaluate its effectiveness, the approach was applied to a case study of the Ballina embankment in New South Wales, Australia. The results show that the method effectively predicts long-term settlement for PVD-improved embankment projects, achieving a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency.

2. Bayesian updating of soft clay settlement

The consolidation of soft clay typically takes a long time, providing an opportunity to monitor settlement and pore water pressure during and after embankment construction. When new monitoring data become available, these data can be used to calibrate the consolidation model parameters. Let $\mathbf{y}_i = [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k]$ denote the monitoring settlement and pore water pressure at varying monitoring time, and y_1 to y_k represent the corresponding i^{th} measurements type at time point 1 to k . Let \mathbf{x} denote the uncertain soil variables, represented by a random vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)^T$, where n is the number of variables. The behaviour of the embankment, including settlement and pore water pressure, can be predicted using the posterior soil parameters to conduct forward prediction. Based on Bayes' theorem, the posterior probability density function (PDF) of soil parameters given monitoring data \mathbf{y}_i , $f^*(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y}_i)$, can be expressed by

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the proposed Class C prediction approach

$$f''(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y}_i) = \frac{L(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y}_i)f'(\mathbf{x})}{\int_{\mathbf{x}}L(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y}_i)f'(\mathbf{x})d\mathbf{x}} \quad (1)$$

where $L(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y}_i)$ is the likelihood function representing the probability of observing the monitoring data \mathbf{y}_i given the soil parameters \mathbf{x} ; and $f'(\mathbf{x})$ is the prior PDF of \mathbf{x} representing the initial beliefs about the soil parameters \mathbf{x} before observing the data \mathbf{y}_i .

2.1. Likelihood function

The measurements, \mathbf{y}_i , and the model predictions $F(\mathbf{x})$ can be connected by likelihood function. If the difference e between $F(\mathbf{x})$ and the

corresponding \mathbf{y}_i is normally distributed with a zero mean, the likelihood function $L(\mathbf{x})$ in Eq. (1) can be presented by

$$L(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{N_d/2} \det(\mathbf{R})^{1/2}} \times \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2}[\mathbf{y}_i - F(\mathbf{x})]^T \mathbf{R}^{-1}[\mathbf{y}_i - F(\mathbf{x})]\right\} \quad (2)$$

where N_d is the number of points for the i^{th} type of measurement (settlement or pore water pressure in this study); \mathbf{R} is the coefficient of variation (COV) of the measurement error corresponding to the monitoring data; \det represents the determinant.

If multiple types of measurements are applied, the errors associated with different types of measurements are assumed to be independent of each other, as they are obtained using different devices. Therefore, the

Table 1
Summary of the parameters for HKIA Chek Lap Kok Test embankment (Yin et al., 2022).

Layer	1	2	3
Thickness (H_i) (m)	3.01	3.21	5.8
Pre-Overburden Pressure (POP) (kPa)	17	17	350
Initial void ratio (e_0)	2.65	2.65	1.06
Unit weight of clay (γ_{clay}) (kN/m ³)	14.22	14.22	19.13
Swelling index (κ)	0.0396	0.0396	0.0224
Compression index (λ)	0.5081	0.5081	0.1339
Creep index (ρ)	0.0078	0.0078	0.0035
t_0 (year)	0.0027	0.0027	0.0027
Vertical permeability (k_v) (m/yr)	0.03469	0.03469	0.09461
Horizontal permeability (k_h) (m/yr)	0.06307	0.06307	0.18922
Drain spacing S_p (m)	1.5	1.5	1.5
Drain pattern	Triangular	Triangular	Triangular
Drain radius (r_d) (m)	0.0275	0.0275	0.0275
Ratio of smear to drain radius (r_s/r_d)	5	5	5
Ratio of undisturbed horizontal permeability to smear zone permeability at drain soil interface (k_{h0}/k_s)	1.82	1.82	2.00

Table 2
Summary of the loading history for HKIA Chek Lap Kok Test embankment (Yin et al., 2022).

Loading sequence	Starting time (day)	Ending time (day)	Vertical pressure changed (kPa)	Loading type
1	0	17	52	Linearly varying with time
2	17	77	0	Uniform load
3	77	96	100	Linearly varying with time
4	96	375	0	Uniform load
5	375	400	-116	Linearly varying with time
6	400	425	0	Uniform load
7	425	575	64	Linearly varying with time
8	575	18,675	0	Uniform load

Fig. 3. Comparison of the settlement presented in (Yin et al., 2022) and obtained by the self-developed program 1DSimp_B.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the average degree of consolidation $U_{multi,j}$ presented in (Yin et al., 2022) and obtained by the in-house program 1DSimp_B

likelihood function is given by

$$L(\mathbf{x}) = \prod_i^N \left\{ \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{N_i/2} \det(\mathbf{R}_i)^{1/2}} \times \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} [\mathbf{y}_i - \mathbf{F}_i(\mathbf{x})]^T \mathbf{R}_i^{-1} [\mathbf{y}_i - \mathbf{F}_i(\mathbf{x})] \right) \right\} \quad (3)$$

where N is the total number of measurement data types. For example, $N = 1$ when only the monitoring settlement or pore water pressure data is used, and $N = 2$ when both the monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data are applied; \mathbf{y}_i and $\mathbf{F}_i(\mathbf{x})$ are the measurements of the i^{th} data type and the corresponding model prediction, respectively. For example, if only monitoring settlement data is utilized, \mathbf{y}_i represents the monitoring settlement data and $\mathbf{F}_i(\mathbf{x})$ is the corresponding settlement obtained by consolidation analysis.

2.2. Subset simulation

Straub and Papaioannou (2015) demonstrated that the Bayesian updating problem in Eq. (1) can be transformed into an equivalent structural reliability problem and then solved by reliability methods. By doing so, an auxiliary space $[\mathbf{x}, p]$ and a domain, Ω , are defined by

$$\Omega = [p - cL(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0] \quad (4)$$

where c is a positive constant number satisfying $cL(\mathbf{x}) \leq 1$, and c is $1/\max(L(\mathbf{x}))$ in this study; p is a random variable drawn from the standard uniform distribution.

Eq. (1) can then be transformed to the domain Ω , which can be expressed by

$$\begin{aligned} f''(\mathbf{x}) &= \frac{L(\mathbf{x})f(\mathbf{x})}{\int_{\mathbf{x}} L(\mathbf{x})f(\mathbf{x})d\mathbf{x}} = \frac{\int_0^{cL(\mathbf{x})} f(\mathbf{x})dp}{\int_{\mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x}) \int_0^1 I[p \leq cL(\mathbf{x})] dp d\mathbf{x}} \\ &= \frac{\int_{p \in \Omega} f(\mathbf{x}) dp}{\int_{\mathbf{x}} \int_0^1 I([\mathbf{x}, p] \in \Omega) f(\mathbf{x}) dp d\mathbf{x}} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $I([\mathbf{x}, p] \in \Omega)$ is the indicator function and

$$I[\mathbf{x}, p] = \begin{cases} 1, & [\mathbf{x}, p] \in \Omega \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The reliability problem in Eq. (5) can be solved by a highly efficient reliability analysis method, SuS, which is proposed by Au and Beck (2001). For convenience, the variables, p and \mathbf{x} , in the auxiliary space Ω are converted into the standard normal space $\mathbf{u} = [u_0, u_1, \dots, u_n]$ where u_i

Fig. 5. Plan view of Ballina embankment (Cross-section 2).

Fig. 6. Profiles of material parameters with depth (Pineda et al., 2016).

Fig. 7. Cross section and instruments locations of Ballina embankment.

(i ranges from 0 to n) are sampled from standard normal distribution. The variables p and \mathbf{x} can then be expressed by \mathbf{u} as

$$p = \Phi(u_0)$$

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{T}(u_1, \dots, u_n) \tag{7}$$

where Φ is the cumulative probability function CDF for the standard normal distribution; \mathbf{T} is the transformation function (Hohenbichler and Rackwitz, 1981; Der Kiureghian and Liu, 1986).

The original auxiliary space Ω can then be transferred to the new observational domain $\Omega_{\mathbf{u}}$

$$\Omega_{\mathbf{u}} = \{ \Phi(u_0) - cL[\mathbf{T}(u_1, \dots, u_n)] \leq 0 \} \tag{8}$$

The limit state function of failure in domain $\Omega_{\mathbf{u}}$, $H(\mathbf{u})$, can be defined as

$$H(\mathbf{u}) = u_0 - \Phi^{-1}\{cL[\mathbf{T}(u_1, \dots, u_n)]\} \tag{9}$$

The intermediate failure domain can be determined by

$$F_i^* = \{H(\mathbf{u}) \leq h_i\} \tag{10}$$

where i ranges from 1 to m ; h_i is the threshold value for the intermediate

Table 3
Basic soil and PVD parameters of Ballina embankment.

Layer	Crust		Estuarine clay			
	1	2	3	4	5	6
H_i (m)	1.5	0.5	2	1	1	4.5
γ_{clay} (kN/m ³)	18.75	15.97	14.7	13.7	14.0	13.7
e_0	0.81	1.63	2.31	3.16	2.89	3.19
Initial over consolidation ratio (OCR)	4.8	3.98	2.33	2.32	2.07	1.84
k_h/k_v	1	1	1	1	1	1
Drain space, S_p (m)	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
Drain pattern	Square	Square	Square	Square	Square	Square
Drain radius, r_d (m)	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025
Ratio of smear zone radius and drain radius, r_s/r_d	5	5	5	5	5	5
Ratio of undisturbed horizontal permeability to smear zone permeability at drain soil interface, k_h/k_s	5	5	5	5	5	5

Table 4
The starting and ending time, vertical pressures and types of the loading sequences for Ballina embankment.

Loading sequence	Starting time (day)	Ending time (day)	Vertical pressure changed (kPa)	Loading type
1	0	1	12.6	Linearly varying with time
2	1	12	0	Uniform load
3	12	20	21.6	Linearly varying with time
4	20	42	0	Uniform load
5	42	55	61.5	Linearly varying with time
6	55	974	0	Uniform load

subset level and can be determined adaptively such that the intermediate conditional probabilities, $P(F_1^*)$ and $P(F_{i+1}^*|F_i^*)$, are equal to p_0 (p_0 is 0.1 in this study), which would lead to $h_1 > h_2 > \dots > h_i > \dots > h_m \leq 0$; m represents the required number of simulation levels in SuS to reach $F_m^* = \{H(\mathbf{u}) \leq h_m\}$.

Once the highest outer subset level m is reached, the failure samples can be extracted from the subset level m and can be considered as seeds to generate N_1 samples satisfying $\{H(\mathbf{u}) \leq h_m\}$, where N_1 is the number of the random samples for the first subset level. The generated failure samples are then the posterior samples. The posterior distributions of the random variables in Bayesian updating can thus be obtained by

Table 5
Summary of the updating schemes.

Updating scheme	Number of monitoring data applied							
	Dataset 1	Dataset 2	Dataset 3	Dataset 4	Dataset 5	Dataset 6	Dataset 7	Dataset 8
Scheme 1: using the monitoring settlement at all monitoring depths	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
	42d	76d	117d	292d	384d	496d	797d	974d
Scheme 2: using both monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data at all monitoring depths	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
	42d	76d	117d	292d	384d	496d	797d	974d

conventional statistical analysis.

3. The one-dimensional general simplified Hypothesis B method

To construct the likelihood function in Eq. (1), the model prediction is required. In Class C prediction approach proposed in this study, the general simplified Hypothesis B method which is based on the 1D EVP model proposed by Yin and Graham (1989) is employed to obtain the model prediction, $F(\mathbf{x})$, in Eqs. (2) and (3). In this method, the average excess pore water pressure is determined by the constitutive partial differential equation derived by Walker and Indraratna (2009), which can be presented by

$$\frac{m_v}{\bar{m}_v} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial t} = - \left[dT_h \frac{\eta}{\bar{\eta}} \bar{u} - dT_v \frac{\partial}{\partial Z} \left(\frac{k_v}{\bar{k}_v} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial Z} \right) \right] + \frac{m_v}{\bar{m}_v} \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}}{\partial t} \quad (11)$$

$$Z = \frac{z}{H}, dT_v = \frac{\bar{c}_v}{H^2}, dT_h = \frac{2\bar{\eta}}{\gamma_w \bar{m}_v}, \bar{c}_v = \frac{\bar{k}_v}{\gamma_w \bar{m}_v}, \eta = \frac{k_h}{r_e^2 \mu}$$

where \bar{u} is the average excess pore pressure at depth z ; $\bar{\sigma}$ is the total stress at depth z ; H is the total depth of the soil profile; m_v is the volume compressibility; k_v and k_h are the vertical and horizontal permeability, respectively; \bar{m}_v , $\bar{\eta}$ and \bar{k}_v are the referenced value of m_v , η and k_v respectively and are considered as the values of m_v , η and k_v at the first layer in this study. Specifically, if PVDs are not installed, $\eta = 0$; r_e is the equivalent radius and varies depending on the drainage pattern (0.525 S_p for drain with triangle pattern and 0.564 S_p for square pattern); S_p is the drain space; μ , which corresponds to the drain and smear zone, can be estimated using Eqs. (12) to (14) under different conditions, as proposed by Walker and Indraratna (2006) and Hansbo et al. (1981). These conditions include:

Cases without smear zone:

$$\mu = \ln(n) - 0.75 \quad (12)$$

Cases with smear zone of constant reduced permeability:

$$\mu = \ln(n/s) + \zeta \ln(s) - 0.75 \quad (13)$$

Cases with a smear zone of parabolically varying permeability:

$$\mu = \ln\left(\frac{n}{s}\right) - \frac{3}{4} + \frac{\zeta(s-1)^2}{(s^2-2\zeta s+\zeta)} \ln\left(\frac{s}{\sqrt{\zeta}}\right) - \frac{s(s-1)\sqrt{\zeta(s-1)}}{2(s^2-2\zeta s+\zeta)} \ln\left(\frac{\sqrt{\zeta}+\sqrt{\zeta-1}}{\sqrt{\zeta}-\sqrt{\zeta-1}}\right) \quad (14)$$

where $n = r_e/r_d$ and $s = r_s/r_d$; r_d and r_s represent drain radius and smear zone radius, respectively; ζ is the ratio of the undisturbed horizontal permeability to the permeability within the smear zone (k_h/k_s).

When considering the effects of the smear zone and well resistance, μ can be calculated by

$$\mu = \frac{n^2}{n^2-1} \left(\ln\frac{n}{s} - \frac{3}{4} + \zeta \ln s \right) + \frac{s^2}{n^2-1} \left(1 - \frac{s^2}{4n^2} \right) + \frac{\zeta}{n^2-1} \left(\frac{s^4-1}{4n^2} - s^2 + 1 \right) + \pi z(2l-z) \frac{k_h}{q_w} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n^2} \right) \quad (15)$$

where $q_w = k_w \pi r_d^2$, k_w is the permeability in drain; l is the length of the PVD.

Fig. 8. Monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data at all depths and the number of data points for various datasets

Table 6

The prior knowledge of the Parameters following lognormal distribution random parameters in Bayesian back analysis.

Layer		Crust		Estuarine clay			
		1	2	3	4	5	6
Compression index	mean	0.043	0.348	0.587	1.304	0.913	1.061
λ	COV	0.3					
Vertical permeability	mean	2.35E-4	2.62E-4	6.66E-4	1.06E-4	9.11E-5	9.80E-5
k_v (m/day)	COV	3.5					

Table 7

The prior knowledge of random parameters following uniform distribution in Bayesian back analysis.

Ratio of λ to κ		Ratio of ϕ to λ		Correction factor	
$\alpha_2 (\lambda/\kappa)$		$\alpha_2 (\phi/\lambda)$		α	
Upper bound	Lower bound	Upper bound	Lower bound	Upper bound	Lower bound
5	10	0.02	0.06	0.6	1

The analytical solution of Eq. (11) which is derived by Walker and Indraratna (2009) based on the spectral method is applied to determine the distribution of the excess pore water pressure. A more detailed calculation process for PVD parameters and for solving Eq. (11) can be found in an EXCEL spreadsheet named SPECCON, developed by Walker and Indraratna (2009).

The total consolidation settlement of the multi-layered viscous soils with vertical drains under any loading conditions, S_{totalB} , can then be calculated by

$$S_{totalB} = S_{primary} + S_{creep} = \sum_{j=1}^{nlay} U_j S_{fj} + \sum_{j=1}^{nlay} [\alpha U_j^\beta S_{creep,fj} + (1 - \alpha U_j^\beta) S_{creep,dj}] \quad (16)$$

where $S_{primary}$ and S_{creep} are primary and creep settlement, respectively; $nlay$ is the number of soil layers at a given location down to the bottom layer (as presented in Fig. 1); U_j and S_{fj} are the average consolidation degree and the final primary settlement for the j^{th} layer, respectively; α and β are the power index range from 0 to 1, and are suggested as 0.8 and 0.3 respectively by Yin et al. (2022); $S_{creep,fj}$ is creep settlement under vertical effective stress at final state; $S_{creep,dj}$ is the delayed creep settlement and only occurs when time $t \geq t_{EOP,field}$ where $t_{EOP,field}$ is the

time at the end of the primary consolidation state for soil layers in field.

When calculating settlement at a specific monitoring location, two potential cases may arise. As shown in Fig. 1, in case 1, if the location is at the boundary (either top or bottom) of a certain soil layer, Eq. (16) can be directly applied to calculate the settlement. In this case, $nlay$ is the number of soil layer from Layer 2 down to Layer n . In case 2, if the location is within a certain soil layer, an additional sublayer is added to effectively treat the location as being at the boundary of the soil layer, allowing Eq. (16) to be used to calculate the corresponding settlement. The $nlay$ is the number of soil layer from Layer 3 to Layer n . The general simplified Hypothesis B method can thus be applied to calculate settlement at any locations. More details about this simplified method and the determination of parameters can be found in Yin et al. (2022). In this study, an in-house 1D consolidation program, *1DSimp_B*, was developed, and its validation is presented in Section 5.

4. Implementation procedure of the proposed approach for Class C prediction

A schematic diagram that summarizes the implementation of the proposed Class C prediction approach which combines BUS with the general simplified Hypothesis B method is given in Fig. 2. The procedure consists of seven main steps.

Step 1: Input embankment geometry information, prior distribution (mean and COV) of soil parameters which need to be calibrated, and input parameters required in BUS (e.g., the number of the random samples (N_i) at each subset level, and p_0).

Step 2: Perform Monte Carlo simulation (MCS) to generate N_i random samples from the prior distribution of soil parameters for initial sampling.

Step 3: Construct the consolidation analysis model and conduct consolidation analysis based on the general simplified Hypothesis B approach at each sample to obtain model predictions (settlement and

Fig. 9. Settlement prediction at different monitoring depths using updating scheme 1 with different dataset applied.

pore water pressure) at the monitoring time points. Determine the measurements (updating scheme).

Step 4: Construct likelihood function and define limit-state function $H(\mathbf{u})$ which is served as bridge to connect Bayesian back analysis to a reliability problem.

Step 5: Calculate $H(\mathbf{u})$ values at initial samples according to Eq. (9), sort the outputs in a descending order, and set h_1 as the threshold value so that the estimation of $P(F_1^+)$ equal p_0 . Move the samples which satisfy $H(\mathbf{u}) > h_1$ into the first subset. Move the rest $p_0 \times N_{\text{samples}}$ which satisfy $H(\mathbf{u}) \leq h_1$ to the second subset.

Step 6: Take the $p_0 \times N_{\text{samples}}$ of the second subset as seeds to generate more samples, then repeat Step 5 at the new samples till the true failure criterion is achieved. Output the samples at the final subset, calculate the posterior mean and COV values of the soil parameters through conventional statistical analysis.

Step 7: Perform forward prediction for long-term settlement and pore water pressure by using the general simplified Hypothesis B approach.

5. Validation of the inhouse 1D consolidation program 1DSimp_B

Based on the generalized simplified Hypothesis B method proposed by Yin et al. (2022), an in-house 1D consolidation program named 1DSimp_B has been developed. Validation of the program is established through comparison with the HKIA Chek Lap Kok test embankment which has been reported by Yin et al. (2022). The soil parameters and the vertical loading history of the HKIA Chek Lap Kok test embankment are presented in Table 1 and Table 2 below respectively. The obtained settlement and average degree of consolidation, $U_{\text{multi},j}$, for each layer are presented in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 respectively. It should be noted that ‘Yin et al. (2022)_d’ and ‘1DSimp_B_d’ represent the results presented in (Yin et al., 2022) and obtained by the self-developed in-house program, 1DSimp_B, at depth d m (d equals to 0, 3 and 6) respectively.

As shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, both the settlements and the average degree of consolidation calculated by 1DSimp_B agree well to the ones reported by Yin et al. (2022) at all depths. This agreement validates the accuracy of ‘1DSimp_B’, enhancing the confidence and reliability of the proposed Class C prediction approach.

Fig. 10. Settlement prediction at different monitoring depths under updating scheme 2 with different dataset applied

6. Ballina embankment

To demonstrate the practical application of the proposed Class C prediction approach, Cross Section 2 of Ballina embankment is considered, where subsoil improvement has been carried out using pre-fabricated vertical drains (PVDs). The crest of the 3-m-high embankment was 83.3 m long with slopes inclined at 1.5H: 1 V (horizontal dimension: vertical dimension). Initially, a 102.9-m-long and 0.6-m-thick working platform was constructed, with a 90.1-m-long, 0.4-m-thick sand drainage layer placed beneath the embankment's footprint. The plan view of the embankment is shown in Fig. 5. Profiles of material characteristics including nature water content, liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL), dry density, and the particle size distribution (PSD) with depth are shown in Fig. 6, which is adapted from Pineda et al. (2016). Based on these data, the stratigraphy of the Ballina embankment can be identified as follows: initially, a 1.5-m-thick alluvium deposit crust clay layer, followed by a 9-m-thick estuarine soft clay layer, and a transition to a sand layer extending to a total depth of 13 m. Various instrumentation devices were deployed to monitor the behaviour of the soil under progressive loading conditions over a period of three years. Settlement

measurements include the surface settlement (at a depth of 0 m), the settlements at depths of 1.5 m, 4.5 m, 7.5 m, 10.5 m, 14.2 m and 18.65 m below the ground level. As reported by Kelly et al. (2018), consolidation settlement has ceased beneath a depth of 10.5 m in the transition zone. However, ongoing consolidation settlement measurements have been recorded in the estuarine clay layer above the depth of 10.5 m, even after three years. Consequently, for the purposes of this study, only the soil layers above 10.5 m (the crust and estuarine clay layers) are considered. The locations of instruments and soil profile are presented in Fig. 7. The model basic parameters of Ballina embankment are summarized into Table 3. It should be noted that the difference between the horizontal and vertical permeability of the Ballina embankment can be ignored and thus the ratio of vertical to horizontal permeability is assumed to be 1, as reported by Kelly et al. (2018). The load sequences of Ballina embankment are presented in Table 4. To investigate the influence of the monitoring data on the performance of the proposed Class C prediction approach, two updating schemes and different number of monitoring data are applied, as summarized in Table 5 and Fig. 8.

As shown in Fig. 8, a significant increase in monitoring pore water pressure at 2 m can be observed after the 200th day, which is attributed

Fig. 11. Predicted time-settlement curves at monitoring depths of 0 m, 1.5 m, 4.5 m and 7.5 m using monitoring settlement data prior to the 76th, 292nd, 496th, 974th day.

to fluctuations in the groundwater level induced by the flooding as reported by Kelly et al. (2018). However, no standpipe piezometers were installed to record changes in groundwater level. Consequently, the fluctuations in groundwater levels induced by the flooding are not reflected in the monitored pore water pressure data.

6.1. Prior distribution of soil parameters in Bayesian back analysis

The parameters listed in Table 3 can be considered deterministic values since they can be confidently determined. The rest of the soil parameters, including OCR, the compression index (λ), swelling index (κ), creep index (φ) and k_v , are treated as random variables characterized by PDFs in Bayesian back analysis. Among these soil parameters, λ and k_v are updated directly in Bayesian back analysis. Considering the ratios, λ/κ and φ/λ , are typically implemented in soft clay designs as reported by Vermeer and Neher (1999), two factors, α_1 and α_2 , where $\alpha_1 = \lambda/\kappa$ and $\alpha_2 = \varphi/\lambda$ are introduced to update κ and φ indirectly. This approach contributes to saving computational time in solving Bayesian

back analysis problem and can avoid situations where λ is smaller than κ or φ is larger than λ in the sampling process, given that the sampling process in BUS is random. The possible ranges for α_1 and α_2 are determined according to the ones suggested by Vermeer and Neher (1999) based on general observations. Additionally, OCRs are determined from laboratory test results without considering the strain rate difference between field and laboratory, which leads to the overestimation of OCRs. A correction factor, α , is thus introduced to account for this overestimation. Considering that λ and k_v can be determined from the lab or field test results, the two parameters are assumed to follow more informed lognormal distribution. For α , α_1 and α_2 , only the possible ranges can be determined. The three factors are thus considered to obey uniform distribution. The prior PDF of the soil parameters following lognormal and uniform distributions are summarized to Table 6 and Table 7, respectively.

Fig. 12. Predicted time-settlement curves at monitoring depths of 0 m, 1.5 m, 4.5 m and 7.5 m using both monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data prior to the 76th, 292nd, 496th, 974th day

6.2. Settlement prediction

6.2.1. Settlement prediction using the mean of posterior samples

In this section, the settlement predictions at the monitoring depths of 0 m, 1.5 m, 4.5 m and 7.5 m under two different updating schemes are presented. Updating scheme 1 uses monitoring settlement data at all depths, while updating scheme 2 incorporates both monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data at all depths. The settlement predictions at depths of 0 m, 1.5 m, 4.5 m and 7.5 m obtained using the posterior mean of soil parameters under updating schemes 1 and 2 are shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, respectively. Based on findings of Kelly et al. (2018), an uncertainty of $\pm 20\%$ in the settlement prediction of the Ballina embankment is considered reasonable, suggesting that achieving prediction accuracy within $\pm 20\%$ is adequate for practical applications. Consequently, an $\pm 20\%$ uncertainty band is also presented alongside the measurements to evaluate the minimum number of monitoring data required to achieve settlement prediction with the desired accuracy.

As illustrated in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, the accuracy of settlement prediction can be enhanced with the incorporation of more monitoring data into the proposed Class C prediction approach. For the two different

updating schemes, the predicted settlements versus time curves fall within the $\pm 20\%$ uncertainty range of the measurements using only 76 days of monitoring data. This demonstrates the capability of the proposed approach to achieve the required accuracy at an early stage of the project timeline. This efficiency makes the approach highly suitable for large-scale infrastructure projects, where timely predictions are crucial for maintaining project progress and avoiding cost overruns.

6.2.2. Settlement prediction based on the whole posterior samples

Additionally, settlement predictions represented by the mean of the predicted settlements from all posterior samples of the soil parameters, based on updating schemes 1 and 2, are shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, respectively. To illustrate the uncertainty in the predicted settlements, the mean \pm one standard deviation is also included.

As shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, incorporating more monitoring data results in a narrower uncertainty band, indicating that increased monitoring data reduces uncertainty in settlement predictions. It is also observed that the predicted settlement curves at all depths, obtained using only the monitoring settlement data (as presented in Fig. 11), exhibit narrower uncertainty bands compared to those using both

Fig. 13. Prior and posterior distribution of λ at each layer using 76 days of monitoring settlement data.

Table 8

Summation of posterior mean and lower and upper bound of λ at soil layers 2 to 6.

Soil layer	Lower bound	Upper bound	Updating scheme 1		Updating scheme 2	
			76d	496d	76d	496d
2	0.304	0.609	0.349	0.354	0.334	0.33
3	0.304	0.609	0.514	0.639	0.551	0.592
4	0.477	1.503	1.308	1.311	1.186	1.335
5	0.477	1.263	0.904	0.889	0.841	0.807
6	0.477	1.263	1.138	1.102	0.945	1.043

monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data (as shown in Fig. 12). This suggests that the incorporation of additional pore water pressure data introduces more variability into the predicted settlements.

6.3. Updated soil parameters

6.3.1. Posterior λ

The prior and posterior PDF of λ at each layer using updating scheme 1 which utilizes monitoring settlement data only and updating scheme 2 which incorporates both monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data based on datasets 76d and 496d are presented in Fig. 13 to Fig. 16. Both the prior and posterior means and standard deviations are included in the legend for comparison. Additionally, as reported by Kelly et al. (2018), λ reaches a peak after yielding and then decreases with increasing stress levels. The upper and lower bounds for λ can then be determined. Due to the limited test results, the bounds for validation are provided only for layers 2 to 6. The mean and standard deviation values for the two updating schemes and datasets 76d and 496d are summarized to Table 8 to illustrate the reasonableness of the updated λ values at soil layers 2 to 6.

As shown in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 when dataset 76d is applied, the posterior means and standard deviations of λ obtained using updating schemes are close to the prior values. This is expected as the prior mean of λ at each layer is derived from the Constant Rate of Strain (CRS) test results, which exhibit less uncertainty. This finding validates the

effectiveness of the Bayesian updating approach proposed in this study. Reliable updated λ values can be obtained by using either monitoring settlement data alone or using both monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data. Additionally, the posterior standard deviations of λ using the two updating schemes are slightly lower than the prior ones, indicating a slight decrease in variability within the posterior distribution.

Although a multimodal posterior distribution is observed in the posterior PDFs at each layer, the posterior mean values for all soil layers are close to the dominant peaks, suggesting the reliability of the posterior PDFs of λ . It can also be observed from Fig. 15 and Fig. 16 that the standard deviations of the updated λ values using dataset 496d are larger than those based on dataset 76d, except for soil layers 5 and 6. This indicates incorporating more monitoring data may introduce additional variations. This is expected as incorporating more monitoring data reveals the complexities and nonlinearities in soil behaviour that were not apparent with limited data. The Bayesian updating model needs to explore a broader parameter space, identifying interactions and correlations between parameters, as well as variability in soil behaviour. This can result in multiple combinations of parameters that can satisfy the observed behaviour, ultimately leading to greater uncertainty in soil parameters.

As shown in Table 8, based on the range values for λ provided by Kelly et al. (2018), the posterior mean values for λ obtained using updating scheme 2 fall within the range for all soil layers. However, the posterior mean value for λ obtained from updating scheme 1 at the third layer exceeds the corresponding upper bound. This indicates that incorporating both monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data can lead to more reasonable updated soil parameters.

6.3.2. Posterior k_v/γ_w

The updated k_v/γ_w at each layer using updating schemes 1 and 2 based on datasets 76d and 496d are shown in Figs. 17 to 20. As illustrated in Fig. 17 and Fig. 18, when the same dataset is used, the posterior mean of k_v/γ_w at each layer, based only on monitoring settlement data is closer to the prior values compared to those obtained using both monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data. This indicates that the updated k_v/γ_w values are significantly influenced by monitoring pore

Fig. 14. Prior and posterior distribution of λ at each layer using 76 days of monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data.

Fig. 15. Prior and posterior distribution of λ at each layer using 496 days of monitoring settlement data.

water pressure data.

Comparing Fig. 17 and Fig. 19 with Fig. 18 and Fig. 20, the variations in the updated k_v/γ_w using both monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data (updating scheme 2) are larger than those obtained using monitoring settlement data only (updating scheme 1) for most soil layers, indicating that incorporating additional pore water pressure data may introduce more variations. This can be explained by the fact that incorporating more monitoring data may reveal more complex interactions between parameters and variations in soil parameters. To account for those complexities, the Bayesian updating model needs to

explore a broader parameter space, identifying interactions and correlations between parameters, as well as variability in soil behaviour. This can result in multiple combinations of parameters that can satisfy the observed behaviour, ultimately leading to greater uncertainty in posterior soil parameters.

Additionally, the quality of monitoring data may influence the degree of uncertainty in the posterior soil parameters. The monitoring pore water pressure data remain unmodified due to the lack of available records. It is also observed that the degree of variation in the posterior k_v/γ_w is much greater than that of λ . This is expected as the COV value in k_v/γ_w

Fig. 16. Prior and posterior distribution of λ at each layer using 496 days of monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data.

Fig. 17. Prior and posterior distribution of k_v/γ_w at each layer using 76 days of monitoring settlement data.

γ_w are much greater than that for λ . This observation is consistent with previous findings by Kelly et al. (2018), which identified k_v as the most uncertain soil parameter.

6.3.3. Posterior $\alpha_1 (\lambda/\kappa)$, $\alpha_2 (\varphi/\lambda)$ and α

The updated $\alpha_1 (\lambda/\kappa)$, $\alpha_2 (\varphi/\lambda)$ and α using updating schemes 1 and 2 based on datasets 76d and 496d are presented in Fig. 21 to Fig. 24. Since the prior distributions of these three factors are assumed to be uniform, the upper and lower bounds are also included.

As shown in Fig. 21 and Fig. 24, when applying datasets 76d and 974d, the posterior mean values for $\alpha_1 (\lambda/\kappa)$ obtained by updating scheme 2 (as presented in Fig. 22 and Fig. 24) are larger than those from updating scheme 1 (shown in Fig. 21 and Fig. 23). Additionally, the uncertainty range, illustrated by one standard deviation, is narrower in updating scheme 2 compared to updating scheme 1. According to the λ and κ values obtained from both CRS and incremental loading (IL) test results reported by Pineda et al. (2016), the larger λ/κ obtained by updating scheme 2 should be more reasonable. This indicates that

Fig. 18. Prior and posterior distribution of k_v/γ_w at each layer using 76 days of monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data.

Fig. 19. Prior and posterior distribution of k_v/γ_w at each layer using 496 days of monitoring settlement data.

incorporating both monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data (updating scheme 2) can lead to more reasonable α_1 values.

As reported by Kelly et al. (2018), the creep index derived from Incremental loading (IL) tests is $4\% \pm 1\%$ of the compression index. As presented in Fig. 21 and Fig. 24, the posterior mean values for α_2 (φ/λ) all fall within this range. This indicates that the reasonable α_2 (φ/λ) can be obtained using either updating scheme 1 or scheme 2.

The factor α is selected as the correction factor to account for the

strain rate effects, with a recommended value of 0.84 by Pineda et al. (2016). As shown in Fig. 21 and Fig. 24, the updated α values obtained using updating scheme 2 (Fig. 22 and Fig. 24) are closer to the 0.84 comparing to those obtained from updating scheme 1 (Fig. 21 and Fig. 23). This suggests that incorporating both monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data results in more reasonable posterior α values.

Fig. 20. Prior and posterior distribution of k_v/γ_w at each layer using 496 days of monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data

Fig. 21. Posterior mean of α_1 (λ/κ), α_2 (ϕ/λ) and α using 76 days of monitoring settlement data.

Fig. 22. Posterior mean of α_1 (λ/κ), α_2 (ϕ/λ) and α using 76 days of monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data.

6.4. Comparison against RSM-based Bayesian back analysis approaches

Tian et al. (2022) and Tian et al. (2023) also performed Class C prediction for the embankment at the same site using RSM-based Bayesian back analysis approaches. Tian et al. (2023) have already conducted a comparative analysis between the pure RSM-based

Bayesian back analysis used in (Tian et al., 2022) and the one integrating both RSM and FEM used in (Tian et al., 2023) for settlement prediction of Ballina embankment. This section aims to extend this existing comparison by incorporating the settlement versus time curve predicted by our proposed approach, using the same parameters, to evaluate its performance compared to the methods used by Tian et al.

Fig. 23. Posterior mean of α_1 (λ/κ) α_2 (ϕ/λ) and α using 496 days of monitoring settlement data.

Fig. 24. Posterior mean of α_1 (λ/κ), α_2 (ϕ/λ) and α using 496 days of monitoring settlement and pore water pressure data

Fig. 25. Comparison of predicted settlement at surface obtained by RSM-based Bayesian back analysis approaches and the proposed approach in this study.

(2022) and Tian et al. (2023).

Both Tian et al. (2022) and Tian et al. (2023) utilized monitoring settlement data prior to the 682nd day for their analysis. For this study, the settlement prediction obtained by the proposed approach in Section 6.2 indicates that monitoring settlement data up to the 76th day is sufficient to achieve acceptable accuracy. Given that only monitoring settlement data were used in (Tian et al., 2022; Tian et al., 2023), the settlement prediction curve employing 76 days of monitoring settlement data (updating scheme 1) is adopted for the proposed approach. The predicted settlements based on the posterior mean of soil parameters are presented in Fig. 25, where the results from the RSM-based approach in

(Tian et al., 2022) is labelled as ‘RSM-based’, the results obtained by using both RSM and FEM in (Tian et al., 2023) is denoted as ‘FEM-based’, and the proposed approach in this study is labelled as ‘this study’.

The comparison in Fig. 25 reveals that the settlement versus time curves obtained by Tian et al. (2022) and Tian et al. (2023), are consistent with the curve derived from the proposed approach in this study. Tian et al. (2023) emphasized the challenges in pre-determining the appropriate order of RSM to achieve consistent settlement predictions with FEM, as well as the computational intensity in FEM evaluations. The proposed approach in this study enables to achieve comparable accuracy at an early stage of the project timeline while reducing computational costs compared to FEM-based Class C prediction frameworks.

7. Conclusion

This study presents an efficient approach for Class C prediction of long-term settlement in soft clays, with a focus on computational efficiency and practical applicability. By integrating Bayesian back analysis with the general simplified Hypothesis B method, the approach successfully bridges the gap between computational feasibility and the demands of large-scale geotechnical projects by enhancing accuracy and consistency compared to surrogate modelling, while also significantly reducing computational costs relative to numerical methods. The proposed approach was successfully applied to a PVD-improved embankment constructed in Ballina, New South Wales, Australia. Two updating schemes based on different types of monitoring data were implemented to investigate the influence of these monitoring data on the long-term settlement predictions and the updating of soil parameters.

The results demonstrate that the approach enables to provide reliable long-term settlement predictions early in the project timeline. Specifically, for the Ballina embankment, it was found that either 76 days of settlement data alone or 76 days of combined settlement and pore water pressure data were sufficient to achieve reliable predictions.

This early predictability is crucial for timely decision-making in geotechnical projects, allowing for necessary interventions and adjustments to be implemented before substantial settlements occur, thereby preventing cost overruns and delays.

The uncertainty in predicted settlement significantly decreases as the amount of monitoring data increases. However, incorporating more monitoring data may lead to greater variability in the updated soil parameters, particularly when additional pore water pressure data is included. While the inclusion of pore water pressure data introduces variability, it also improves the accuracy of the updated soil parameter estimates. Using monitoring settlement only may lead to unreasonable posterior soil parameters.

The performance of the proposed approach is compared with both RSM and FEM-based Bayesian back analysis approaches. The proposed approach demonstrates comparable accuracy to these methods while offering improvements in both accuracy and consistency compared to RSM-based methods, as well as enhanced efficiency relative to FEM-based approaches. This makes it a valuable tool for predicting long-term settlements in soft clays, providing reliable results with reduced computational demands.

The proposed approach can be extended to two-dimensional applications by incorporating the general simplified Hypothesis B method for two-dimensional conditions, as proposed by Chen et al. (2023). Future research will explore this extension to effectively integrate spatially distributed monitoring data, further enhancing the method's applicability in complex geotechnical scenarios.

The approach is also applicable to PVD-unimproved soft clays, where the PVD-unimproved case can be treated as a simplified scenario of the PVD-improved case with $\eta = 0$. Given the scope of the current study, future research will investigate the application of the proposed method to PVD-unimproved clays, expanding its versatility in settlement prediction.

As the general simplified Hypothesis B method assumes uniform soil conditions within each layer remain constant, it may limit the applicability of the proposed approach to highly heterogeneous soil profiles.

Additionally, a novel static website will be developed using Amazon Web Services (AWS) with an EC2 instance to support the proposed approach. This website will provide a user-friendly interface for engineers tackling the complex challenge of predicting soft clay settlements while maintaining reasonable computational costs.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Shan Huang: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jinsong Huang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Richard Kelly:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Merrick Jonse:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Patrick Wong:** Writing – review & editing. **Stanley Yuen:** Writing – review & editing. **A.H.M. Kamruzzaman:** Writing – review & editing. **Shui-Hua Jiang:** Software, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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